

A New Name for *Cereus* *haitiensis* A.R.Franck & Peguero (Cactaceae)

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER¹

Abstract

Cereus haitiensis A.R.Franck & Peguero is an illegitimate later homonym of *Cereus haitiensis* (K.Schum.) Schelle. The replacement name *Cereus ayisyen* is proposed.

Zusammenfassung

Cereus haitiensis A.R.Franck & Peguero ist ein illegitimes späteres Homonym von *Cereus haitiensis* (K.Schum.) Schelle. Der Ersatzname *Cereus ayisyen* wird vorgeschlagen.

Samenvatting

Cereus haitiensis A.R.Franck & Peguero is een onwettig later homoniem van *Cereus haitiensis* (K.Schum.) Schelle. De vervangende naam *Cereus ayisyen* wordt voorgesteld.

Keywords

Cactaceae, *Cereus*, Nomenclature

In 2017 the name *Cereus haitiensis* A.R.Franck & Peguero was proposed for a *Cereus* Mill. (Cactaceae) species endemic to Haiti (Franck & al. 2017). The authors acknowledged that the same binary combination had been used before by Schelle (1907: 89), but dismissed it as a nomen nudum.

It is not. The name was validated both by Schelle himself, who provided a brief description in Schelle 1926 (120), and by Backeberg (1959: 780), who gave a full and direct reference to the basionym, *Cereus grandiflorus* (L.) Mill. var. *haitiensis* K.Schum., which is validated by a brief description as well (Schumann 1903: 183). Hence, *Cereus haitiensis* (K.Schum.) Schelle was validly published and *Cereus haitiensis* A.R.Franck & Peguero is an illegitimate later homonym under ICN Art. 53.1.

¹ Roggekamp 379
NL-2592 VV Den Haag
mhjvandermeer@gmail.com

A replacement name is proposed here:

Cereus ayisyen M.van der Meer **nom. nov. pro** *Cereus haitiensis* A.R.Franck & Peguero – *Phytoneuron* 2017-29: 2, nom. illeg., **non** *Cereus haitiensis* (K.Schum.) Schelle. Etymology: *ayisyen* is the Hatian Creole translation of *haitiensis*, ‘Haitian’.

The identity of *Cereus haitiensis* (K.Schum.) Schelle is unclear. Schelle (1907: 89) listed this taxon and *Cereus ×maynardiae* (Paxton) Schelle as hybrids between *Cereus grandiflorus* (L.) Mill. and *Cereus speciosus* Cav. [i.e. *×Disoselenicereus nothus* (Siedhof) M.van der Meer] that were both known in German as *rote Königin der Nacht*, ‘red queen of the night’. Weingart on the other hand considered it identical to *Cereus urbanianus* Gürke & Weing. [= *Selenicereus urbanianus* (Gürke & Weing.) Britton & Rose] (Vaupel 1918: 99).

Literature

- Areces-Mallea A. (2018). *Neohaiticereus* a New Subgenus for the Rediscovered Cereae Depicted in Plumier's Plate 26 of the Botanicon Americanum. *Cact. Succ. J.* (Los Angeles) 90(2): 107-118.
<https://doi.org/10.2985/015.090.0206>
- Backeberg C. (1959). *Die Cactaceae. Band II.* Jena: VEB Gustav Fischer Verlag.
<https://www.cactuspro.com/biblio/en:backeberg>
- Franck A.R., Peguero B., Cinea W. & Jestrow B. (2017). A New Species of *Cereus* s.str. (Cactaceae) Endemic to Haiti. *Phytoneuron* 2017-29: 1-17.
<http://www.phytoneuron.net/2017Phytoneuron/29PhytoN-Cereushaitiensis.pdf>
- Guiggi A. (2018). *Serrulatocereus* Guiggi. A New Proposed Genus for the Recent Re-evaluated *Cereus serruliflorus* Haworth From Haiti (Cactaceae). *Cactology* 5(Suppl. 6): 1-4.
[http://www.cactus-mall.com/cactology/Cactology%20V%20\(Suppl%20VI\).pdf](http://www.cactus-mall.com/cactology/Cactology%20V%20(Suppl%20VI).pdf)
- Schelle E. (1907). *Handbuch der Kakteenkultur.* Stuttgart: Eugen Ulmer.
<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/bibliography/84428>
- Schelle E. (1926). *Kakteen.* Tübingen: Alexander Fischer Verlag.
- Schumann K. (1903). Reiseerinnerungen vom Jahre 1903. *Monatsschrift für Kakteenkunde* 13: 182-189.
<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/49692>
- van der Meer M.H.J. (2018). 16 New Nothogenera and 15 New Combinations in Hylocereeae (Cactaceae). *Cactologia Phantastica* 1: 1-17.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2543879>
- Vaupel F. (1918). Änderungen und Nachträge. *Monatsschrift für Kakteenkunde* 28: 99-101.
<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/49698>
- Wisnev M.A. (2018). *Arecesocereus* a New Subgenus of *Cereus*. *Cact. Succ. J.* (Los Angeles) 90(3): 222-223.
<https://doi.org/10.2985/015.090.0301>